

PREFORM COMPACTION AND DEFORMATION DURING THROUGH-THE-THICKNESS IMPREGNATION

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1 Introduction and Fundamentals

Current market studies identified the Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) and RTM-like processes as the most promising approaches for an expanded industrial usage of fiber reinforced plastics in the next 10-20 years. Especially the high automation and short cycle times in ranges of minutes are important advantages. It is assumed that in the next 10 years cost reductions for RTM-processed parts will be mainly due to process improvements (40%). Therefore, a further optimization of these processes is required, comprising all steps of the process chain. [1]

The most important process step is certainly the impregnation of the dry textile with the liquid matrix. In this context almost all approaches dealing with the process parameter selection, process simulation, and textile selection are based on Darcy's law. This law is used to describe the impregnation of the textile with the liquid matrix since it correlates the flow velocity of a liquid in a porous structure (\vec{v}) with the present pressure gradient ($\vec{\nabla}p$), the fluid viscosity (η), and the permeability of the textile (K).

$$\vec{v} = -\frac{K}{\eta} \vec{\nabla}p \quad (1)$$

According to this law an increase of the flow velocity can be achieved through higher pressure values. But this is not always true. Some concepts, currently growing in importance, provide only few pre-compaction and an impregnation through-the-thickness in order to shorten flow paths and reduce cycle times (e.g. VARI, Advanced RTM, wet pressing etc.). When high injection pressures and relatively few pre-compaction go together, a preform compaction/deformation can occur if the pre-compaction is exceeded by the pressure of the resin on the textile. Also deformations can occur due to

the flow induced pressure drop caused by the flow resistance of the fabric itself. It can be referred to such phenomena as hydrodynamic deformation. In such cases knowledge about the permeability is not sufficient for detailed description of the impregnation process.

Fig. 1 illustrates the problem: The compaction, quantified by the fiber volume content (V_F), increases with increasing pressure applied to the fabric (Fig. 1, B, curve 1). On the other side the permeability is negatively correlated to V_F (Fig. 1, B curve 2). Therefore, the initially positive effect of increasing injection pressures on the flow velocity as stated by Darcy's law (Fig. 1, A) can turn around. This states an optimization problem for the selection of process parameters, especially the injection pressure (Fig. 1, C). The phenomenon does not only impede accurate process parameter and material selection. It can also cause severe errors when measuring through-the-thickness permeability at a relatively low V_F . But despite the relevance for the process efficiency, only few approaches exist, which take hydrodynamic compaction into account for the description of the impregnation behavior of textiles (e.g. [2-4]). Often only permeability is considered while the possibility of deformation-induced change of V_F is neglected during measurement and in processes. In this study experiments with conventional measurement equipment are combined with a newly developed measurement approach in order to investigate this phenomenon. At first the influence of several process and textile parameters on the compaction behavior of saturated and unsaturated fabric stacks was tested with a universal testing machine. The results were compared with previous studies concerning the influence of textile parameters on the permeability. This allows a statement about parameters having an influence on the probability of hydrodynamic deformation. Then

the saturated and unsaturated compaction tests were compared with tests carried out using a new measurement cell, at which the flow-induced compaction of preforms was measured. This showed if the estimation of impregnation behavior based on conventional compaction tests is adequate or if more complex systems are required. Finally, unsaturated permeability tests were compared with saturated permeability values calculated from the new cell including the hydrodynamic compaction. Thereby, new insights in the behavior of textiles during impregnation at a low initial V_F were gained.

2 Experimental set-up

Hydrodynamic compaction mainly comprises compaction and impregnation. Therefore, experimental equipment for both effects is required. On the one side separate tests were performed with an out-of-plane permeability measurement device and a universal testing machine for the compaction. On the other side hydrodynamic compaction tests were performed with a new device, allowing a simultaneous investigation of both effects.

2.1 Compaction tests

The pressure required to set a certain V_F of different textiles was investigated with a *ZWICK 1474* universal testing machine. Using the Software TestXpert a test specification was defined, comprising the maximum V_F , the compaction velocity (1 mm/min), and the holding time before relaxation (2 min). For all measurements time, force, and vertical movement were measured. Fig. 2 shows the set-up for the measurements of the preforms. Knowing the density of the textile as well as the area weight, a calculation of V_F based on the absolute distance of the two measuring plates is possible. The measured force was converted into pressure using the area of the preforms. The preforms were circular shaped with a diameter of 100 mm (Fig. 2-(1)). They were cut with an industrial scale cutter of the Bullmer Spezialmaschinen GmbH. The preforms had a smaller area than the measuring plates (Fig. 2-(2, 3)), in order to avoid inaccuracies through inhomogeneous deformation at the edges of the plates. After placing a stack of layers between the plates, the upper plate moved downwards with a constant velocity (1 mm/min, according to [5]). The

recording of the data started when an initial compressive force of 5 N was reached since the accuracy of the system is about 2 N. The stack was compressed to a V_F of about 0.60-0.65, if the limiting maximum force of 20,000 N was not previously reached. The inherent measurement error caused by the compression of the load cell was taken into account by the subtraction of blind curves performed without textiles between the plates before each series of measurements. Each measurement constellation was repeated twice for statistical coverage.

The effect of process and material parameters was investigated. The following process parameters were considered: compaction velocity, number of consecutive compaction cycles, number of layers, shearing angle, stacking sequence, and grade of saturation. To investigate the influence of saturation, the preforms were placed in a bath of rapeseed oil for two hours to ensure a complete substitution of the air through the oil. The saturated stacks were placed between the plates and the measurement was carried out immediately. The oil could flow out of the stack unhindered. Also the textile parameters yarn density, linear density, finish, and type of weave for the woven glass fiber fabrics, and stitching yarn density, yarn count, yarn type, and fiber direction ($\pm 45^\circ$, $0^\circ/90^\circ$) for the non-crimp carbon fiber fabrics were investigated.

2.2 Hydrodynamic compaction tests

It can be assumed, that the simultaneity and interdependence of compaction and impregnation during the process could make separate investigations insufficient for accurate process simulation. Therefore, measurements were carried out with a newly developed measurement cell (patent procedure pending), enabling the simultaneous investigation of compaction and impregnation. A cross section of the measurement cell is illustrated in Fig. 3:

The cell mainly comprises a lower (4) and an upper (1) assembly group. The cavity is surrounded by a lower (11) and an upper (2) distribution media (currently perforated aluminum discs) which ensure an aerial impregnation of the textile and also allow a pre-compaction of the textile in the cavity. The height of the cavity is set by distance elements (8) and is fixed by eight fittings (7). A distribution

chamber (10, 12) ensures a complete in-plane distribution of the measurement liquid before the textile is flown through. The measurement liquid is injected at the inlet (5) and - after passing the textile preform in the cavity - leaves through the vent (6). Ring elements can be placed in the notches (3) in the upper and the lower half in order to have an enhanced compaction of the textile at the edge zone preventing in-plane flow out of the cavity. An additional sealing ring (9) ensures that no measurement liquid leaves the cell on another way than through the vent. Pressure sensors are placed in the lower and the upper distribution chamber, which allows the precise measurement of the pressure drop caused by the flow through the textile. The loss of pressure due to the distribution media was neglected, since it is smaller than the error value of the pressure sensors in the given range of flow rates.

While the upper distribution media is fixed, the lower one is moveable in vertical direction and also slightly spring-loaded (about 2.5 N). If the pressure drop, which is caused by the flow-resistance of the fabric, exceeds the pre-compaction, a further compaction of the textile will occur. The slight suspension of the distribution media (not shown in the image) ensures that it is always in contact with the textile. Therefore, a measurement of the displacement of the distribution media corresponds to a measurement of the compaction of the textile. The displacement is measured by three linear variable differential transformers (LVDT, not shown in the image), allowing not only a statement about the current cavity height, but also about the homogeneity of the compaction. The massive fixation of the cavity height (7) ensures that the displacement measurement is not falsified by relative movements of the upper and the lower cell half. The suspension is extremely smooth, allowing a V_F corresponding to a nearly fully relaxed state and is therefore neglected. Also a pressure system allowing the regulation of the injection pressure and a flowmeter, measuring the volume of the liquid flowing through the cavity, are part of the system. The measurement is controlled and the sensor data is captured by a Labview-based software while the analysis of the data and the calculation of the permeability follow in an Excel-based software tool. The behavior of the flown through textiles is observed varying process parameters like the injection pressure. At the beginning the pre-

compaction is about $V_F = 0.38$ at a cavity height of 5 mm. Different injection pressures are subsequently applied, so that each measurement allows the calculation of the permeability and the flow-induced V_F at different intervals. The displacement values of the three LVDTs and the pressure drop values as well as the evaluation intervals are shown in Fig. 4.

In a second step the cavity height is reduced to 3 mm and the number of layers is subsequently adjusted to get a V_F of about 0.55-0.56, respectively 0.47-0.49. The calculated permeability is correlated with the apparent V_F , which is calculated out of the areal weight of the fabric, the material density and the cavity height at the beginning reduced by the displacement of the lower distribution disc. Thereafter, the same procedure is repeated twice with a new stack.

2.3 Permeability tests

As pointed out above the permeability studies were carried out using different systems. Some are based on an unsaturated measurement principle, where a liquid (rapeseed oil) is injected into a dry textile. These systems require the knowledge of the progression of the flow front over time for the calculation of the permeability [6, 7]. The system used here is based on the usage of ultrasound technology for the monitoring of the flow front height of the point-injected liquid. A description can be found in [8]. These results were compared to permeability values measured with the new measurement cell, which combines a saturated measurement principle with monitoring of flow-induced deformation. This initially dissolves a main problem of all through-the-thickness permeability measurements: The danger of compaction during measurement, which changes the V_F and would lead to severely wrong correlations of V_F and permeability. The moveable disc (Fig. 3, 11) allows the calculation of the true V_F at any time. Also the impregnation over the complete surface, ensured through the distribution media, impedes local deformation. This allows reliable permeability measurements at a very low V_F , which is highly relevant for manufacturing processes with few or no pre-compaction. Thereby, the permeability is separately calculated for every interval given through the steps of increasing pressure gradients (Fig. 4). The values are averaged for each interval.

For the calculation of the permeability the capturing of sensor data concerning the pressure gradient and the volume flow as well as knowledge of the viscosity of the liquid and the cavity height are necessary. According to Darcy's law (Eq. 1) the calculation of the through-the-thickness permeability is then possible based on the following equation:

$$K = \frac{q \cdot \eta \cdot \Delta x}{A \cdot \Delta p} \quad (2)$$

with q being the volumetric flow, A being the flown through cross section, Δp being the pressure gradient and Δx being the flown through length respectively the cavity height.

2.4 Materials

Several carbon fiber non-crimp fabrics and glass fiber woven fabrics were taken into account, representing a wide range of textile parameters. They were carefully selected so that material pairs could be compared, only differing in one single parameter, which makes an isolated investigation of the influence of the parameter on the measured permeability and compaction behaviour possible. The material data is listed in Table 2 for the woven fabrics and in Table 3 for the non-crimp fabrics. As liquid for the permeability measurements a rapeseed oil was used, for which the viscosity depending on the temperature was investigated using a *Brookfield* spindle-rheometer *DV-II+ Pro* with a *LVI* spindle.

3 Results

The results presented here allow a statement about the influence of process and textile parameters on the hydrodynamic deformation behavior of textiles. An excerpt of the measured compaction pressures is listed in Table 1 & Table 2. Cross-comparisons with results gained with the new measurement cell give new insights on the effects of the simultaneity of flow and compaction on the textile behavior during the impregnation process.

3.1 Influences of process parameters on compaction probability

Concerning the process parameters different factors with presumable influence on the probability of hydrodynamic compaction were found:

- An alternating stacking sequence

- An increasing number of consecutive compaction cycles
- An increasing shearing angle
- An increasing number of layers
- An increasing grade of saturation
- A decreasing compaction velocity

The injection pressure is not explicitly listed above as an influencing process parameter, since the correlation between increasing compaction pressures and the grade of compaction, given through the V_F is obvious. This is also true for the pre-compaction of a textile, since a lower pre-compaction naturally goes together with less pressure required for further compaction.

The influence of an alternating stacking sequence was investigated for the non-crimp material no. CF-5. Samples of 6 layers were stacked. Thereby, one group was stacked with always the same orientation, while the other group was stacked with an angle orientation difference of 45° between the single layers. This increases the forces for the setting of a certain V_F , which can be explained by the reduction of possibilities for nesting. For example the pressure at a V_F of 0.50 was raised from 1.31 bar to 1.82 bar in average. However, Hammami et al. [9] had contrary findings when investigating saturated stacks of unidirectional non-crimp fabrics with an $0^\circ/90^\circ$ sequence.

Kelly et al. [10] have shown that between 0.5 mm/min and 5 mm/min the compaction forces increase with the compaction velocity (for dry and wetted textiles). This is confirmed by Kim et al. [11] for dry textiles. Because of inertia of the textiles an increase of compaction resistance with higher velocities seems natural. However, within this study an investigation of the glass fiber woven fabrics no. GF-8 and GF-12 when compacted at 0.5, 2, and 10 mm/min in a dry state showed no tendency. An irrelevance of the velocity on the measured compaction forces for dry textiles was also stated by Saunders et al. [12] for velocities between 0.05 and 1 mm/min. But their experiments showed a strong influence of the velocity when the preforms were saturated – higher velocities then caused higher forces.

The influence of an increasing number of consecutive compaction cycles was investigated for the non-crimp materials CF-1 and CF-5. This factor is of importance, because consecutive compaction can result from e.g. the preforming process. The

time between two cycles was about 25 s. A reduction of the pressure for the setting of a certain V_F could be shown up to the maximum number of cycles (18) for both materials. However, the reduction strongly stagnates. For example when compacting material CF-5 the pressure required to set a V_F of 0.5 is 35 % lower at the second cycle compared to the first one, but only 1 % lower for the 16th cycle compared to the 15th. This behavior can be explained through an uncompleted relaxation between the cycles (viscoelastic behavior) and a permanent deformation of the textiles. Corresponding results were also found by Robitaille et al. [13]. A model describing the viscoelastic behavior of textiles (neglecting permanent deformation) can be found in [10].

The statements to the influence of the number of layers in literature are various. Often a reduction of the required pressure with an increasing number of layers and also a stagnation of this effect for higher numbers of layers is stated. The upper limit for this effect was e.g. found to be at 5 respectively 10 layers by Saunders et al. [12] respectively Chen et al. [14]. This can be explained through the increasing possibilities for nesting, caused by the increasing number of inter-layer boundaries. In this study the results for the non-crimp material CF-5 and for the glass fiber woven textiles GF-8 and GF-12 confirm that higher layer numbers reduce the pressures required for a certain V_F . For example for material CF-5 the pressure required to set a V_F of 0.5 is in average 3.52 bar for 3 layers, 1.56 bar for 7 layers, 1.15 bar for 14 layers, and 1.01 bar for 20 layers. Due to a relatively high variation between the single samples a clear statement about the upper limit of layers where this effect occurs, is not possible, but tends to be about 10 layers for the material no. CF-5 and between 5 and 9 for the glass fiber woven fabrics. Hammami et al. [9] investigated saturated preforms and their results showed no specific tendency. Robitaille et al. [15] could show an influence, which also stagnates at higher numbers of layers. However, they state a higher V_F for constant pressures when the number of layers decreases.

A further parameter, which can have influence on the behavior of a textile is draping, especially shearing. Shearing occurs, when two-dimensional textiles are formed into a three-dimensional shape.

They increase the area weight and therefore the V_F for constant cavity heights. In this study it was investigated if the geometrical differences, besides the higher V_F , have an influence on the compaction behavior. Therefore, all the non-crimp carbon fiber materials were manually sheared to a shearing angle of 10° and afterwards the circular preforms for the compaction tests were cut. Almost all materials showed an increase of the required pressures for a certain V_F with increasing shearing angles. E.g. the increase of the pressure to set a V_F of 0.5 is about 49 % for material CF-6. Only material CF-4 did not show any tendency. This suits the predictions of Lomov et al. [16] who used a geometrical model to show that nesting is reduced by shear deformation, which explains the increased resistance against deformation.

An issue that is especially relevant in the context of hydrodynamic compaction is the influence of saturation on the compaction behavior. Therefore, it was investigated for the glass fiber woven textiles GF-6, GF-7, GF-8, GF-9, and GF-10. All samples showed a reduction of the pressure for a certain V_F when they were saturated. The reduction for the setting of a V_F of 0.5 was between 30 % and 70 %. This confirms the findings of the majority of other studies [3, 5, 10, 11] and can be assigned to the improved lubrication between the fibers and yarns, which reduces the forces required for nesting.

The knowledge of these correlations allows the assessment of manufacturing processes for composites and preforms concerning the sensitivity for hydrodynamic compaction. In general they point out, that few pre-compaction, high injection pressure (eventually caused by high tool closing velocity), few shearing, a high number of layers, homogeneous stacking, consecutive compaction cycles, and a high degree of saturation tend to increase the degree of hydrodynamic deformation.

3.2 Influences of textile parameters on compaction probability

Influences of textile parameters on the compaction behavior were investigated for the glass fiber woven textiles and for the carbon fiber non-crimp fabrics. For the non-crimp fabrics the results were as follows:

Within this study no influence of the stitching type could be found when comparing the materials CF-1

(hybrid) and CF-4 (chain) which only differ concerning the stitching type.

Material CF-1 and CF-3, which are identical except for the stitching length, (2.9 mm respectively 5 mm) show clear differences. To reach a V_F of 0.5 a pressure of 0.76 bar has to be applied to material CF-3, which is more than double compared to material CF-1 (0.30 bar). Therefore, it can be concluded, that an increasing stitching length decreases the probability of hydrodynamic compaction. The higher yarn width resulting from the higher stitching length could cause this effect by reducing nesting effects between single layers.

The stitching yarn, which keeps the carbon fiber yarns in their position, can also have an influence on the compaction behavior. Material CF-1 equals material CF-2 except for the stitching yarn, which has a higher mass and linear density for material CF-2. This leads to slightly higher compaction pressures.

Some of the fabrics also differ concerning the fiber orientations. Material CF-2 and CF-5 respectively material CF-3 and CF-6 can be compared in order to estimate the influence of the orientation (CF-2, CF-3: $\pm 45^\circ$; CF-5, CF-6: $0^\circ/90^\circ$). While the comparison of CF-5 and CF-2 showed clearly higher pressures for the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ orientation, the values for CF-6 and CF-3 do not allow the statement of a tendency. Differences can arise from the changed angle of the seams - which are always oriented in production direction (0°) - to the yarns.

For the glass fiber woven textiles the study showed the following results:

A comparison of the materials GF-6 and GF-7 as well as GF-12 and GF-10 which only differ concerning the type of weave (plain / twill-2/2) showed that twill weaved fabrics have a higher resistance against compaction. The pressure required to set a V_F of 0.5 is increased by 112 % / 37 %.

The linear density was investigated through a comparison of the materials GF-1, GF-2, and GF-3. While the average linear density (average of yarn density in weft and warp direction) increases, the pressure required to set a V_F of 0.50 is reduced. Thereby, a doubling of the linear density causes a pressure reduction of 85 %.

The compaction behavior of the materials GF-13 and GF-14 was examined to investigate the influence of the yarn density. A 21 %-reduction caused a

doubling of the pressure at a V_F of 0.50. This can be explained by the higher inherent density of the fabric with the higher yarn density, requiring less yarn deformation for the same V_F . Also reduced nesting, as stated for the higher stitching length at the CF-tests, could be an explanation.

The influence of the finish was investigated by the materials GF-15, GF-16, GF-17. The finish FK801 which is described as "softer handle" version has a comparably low pressure at a V_F of 0.50. FK600 must be a relatively hard one, causing a poor deformability of the yarns and perhaps a higher friction coefficient. All in all the finish has a very strong influence on the compaction behavior.

A first statement about the influencing textile parameters of hydrodynamic compaction can be derived from these results. This statement can be further refined by a correlation to previous studies, where the influence of textile parameters on the permeability was investigated, since a low permeability increases the pressure drop occurring when a textile is flown through. Mitschang et al. [17] state that twill fabrics have a lower permeability than plain fabrics and therefore lead to higher pressure drops. Since twill fabrics also have a higher resistance against compaction, the sensitivity for hydrodynamic compaction could be the same. Mitschang et al. also state that a higher yarn density seems to increase the permeability. However, the resistance against compaction is decreased, so again no general statement about the influence on the hydrodynamic behavior is possible. For linear and yarn density an interdependent influence on K3 was found by Mitschang et al. Further research is required to investigate this issue for compaction behavior.

Although these compaction tests give an overview about the influences on hydrodynamic compaction, they may be not sufficient to provide secured data e.g. for simulation or parameter value selection. To investigate this issue, a comparison with the new measurement device was carried out. This showed if the consideration of simultaneous flow is necessary.

3.3 Hydrodynamic compaction and permeability behavior

The results concerning the influence of the grade of saturation on the compaction forces have already

shown that the presence of liquid affects the compaction behavior of the textile. This is also true for the permeability which can differ when measured in an unsaturated respectively saturated state due to the influence of capillary effects and changed flow mechanisms inside and outside the yarns. For authentic applications it is also important to answer the question, how textiles behave if they are not only saturated during compaction, but actually flown through by a liquid, like it is the case during manufacturing. To investigate this topic the compaction behavior and the permeability of the glass fiber woven textiles GF-6, GF-7, GF-8, and GF-9 was measured with the new measurement device. These textiles were selected because they represent a wide range of values for the textile parameters investigated in 3.2. If the simultaneous flow has no influence, the results should correspond to the compaction curves generated with the universal testing machine and the permeability values measured by Mitschang et al. [17].

In the new measurement cell a pressure drop occurs when the fabric is flown through. This pressure drop causes a flow-induced compaction. The V_F of the fabric for different pressure drops is compared with the V_F resulting from corresponding pressures applied to the fabrics by the plates of the universal testing machine. For all four materials the pressure drop required for a certain V_F is much higher than the corresponding pressure value applied by the universal testing machine, when the pre-compaction is very low (about $V_F = 0.38$). This can be seen exemplarily in Fig. 5 & Fig. 6, where the hydrodynamic tests at a low V_F are marked by crosses. The higher number of layers used for the measurements with the new measurement cell cannot be the reason for these differences, since that should have a contrary effect (3.1). Also for material GF-8 tests were carried out with 34 and 17 layers, whereas the differences between the results were not bigger than between the single measurements with 17 layers. Therefore, it can be stated, that a simultaneous flow has a tremendous influence on the compaction behavior of a textile. The resistance against compaction increases through the fluid flow compared to a dry or a wetted state. Also the variation between the single measurements is very high (the dashed curves are the regression curves of the repetitive measurements), which means that

reproducibility of the behavior in real manufacturing processes is problematic. This may be solved by consecutive cycles of pre-compaction of the textiles as shown in 3.1. For material GF-6 also a possible reason for the deviations is the relatively uneven compaction of the material during the first measurement. The difference between the values measured by the three LVDT was 0.45 mm at a total average displacement of the distribution disc of 0.63 mm in the worst case (at the highest pressure gradient). In the second measurement the difference was only about 0.09 mm at a total average displacement of 0.90 mm. The uneven displacement makes the curve unreliable. However in most cases the deviation is very low and cannot be the reason for the differences. The curves of the pressure gradient and the three displacement sensors over time are shown in Fig. 4 for the material GF-6, including the intervals for analysis and permeability calculation.

At the middle V_F – values the textiles have shown a flow-induced compaction which is neither predictable on the basis of the tests with the universal testing machine, nor with the tests at lower values for V_F . Material GF-6 shows few compaction at low pressure drops as shown in Fig. 5. But after a certain limit is exceeded, the compaction curve follows a common route. This points out that at a certain point the pre-compaction is exceeded. Material GF-8 shows a corresponding behavior, while material GF-7 shows almost no further compaction. In Fig. 6, where the behavior of material GF-9 is shown, the flow-induced compaction immediately starts when an injection pressure is applied. According to the curves measured with the very low pre-compaction, one would not expect such a behavior. A possible explanation is that the measurements at all three initial V_F – ranges were carried out with the same stack. As explained in 3.1 such consecutive compaction cycles reduce the resistance against deformation. Another possibility which should be investigated is that this phenomenon could be caused by different flow rates at the same pressure gradients (resulting from different layer numbers). For example for material GF-9 the flow rate is about 13.3 ml/s at a pressure gradient of about 0.8 bars and a V_F of 0.49 during the measurement with 9 layers. On the other side during the measurement with 11 layers, there is a flow rate of 8.88 ml/s at a similar

pressure gradient and a V_F of 0.45. This could be an indication, that not only simultaneous flow influences the compaction behavior, but also differing flow rates can induce differing compaction behavior.

When applying high pre-compaction all textiles showed the same behavior. Within the range of pressure drops measured, no remarkable further compaction occurred, since the pressure drop is simply too small to further compact the materials while they are simultaneously flown through. Only a very slight compaction is possible.

The experiments performed with the four glass fiber woven textiles, described in the previous section, were also used to calculate the permeability. Due to the flow-induced compaction at different pressure drops, each measurement delivers permeability values at different V_F .

In general the single measurements with the new cell showed only little deviation, as it can be exemplarily seen in Fig. 7 for material GF-8. However, when the initial V_F is very low, the deviation is higher than when measuring at a higher V_F . When extrapolating the results of the measurements at low initial V_F -values (< 0.45), they show smaller values than the results from the unsaturated measurements performed by Mitschang et al. [17] with the same materials. On the other side, the values measured with the new cell at higher V_F -values are slightly higher than those of the unsaturated measurement. In literature explanations for such deviations are often based on e.g. geometrical rearrangements, air entrapments, capillarity [18]. The different cavity heights (3 mm vs. 8 mm) leading to different numbers of layers at the same V_F could also cause differences, but further research is required to investigate this topic. The measurements at middle V_F -values of about 0.47 line up with the regression curve of the unsaturated measurement at high pressure drops. However, at low pressure drops the values are too high. The slope of the curve is too high to be only caused by the increase in fiber volume content. This is very clear when regarding the measurements at high V_F -values where the hydrodynamic compaction is practically zero (Fig. 5, Fig. 6). It seems that the permeability values measured are pressure-dependent. A phenomenon, contradictory to Darcy's law, which states that higher pressure gradients result in corresponding

higher flow velocities, leaving the permeability value constant. However, as can be seen by these results a pressure-influence on the measured permeability value exists. This means, that the pressure-gradient changes the material behavior, even if the height of the stack maintains unchanged. This confirms the findings of Klunker et al. [2] who stated, that the flow through a stack of textile layers leads to a inhomogeneous distribution of the V_F .

4 Discussion

The results have shown that some manufacturing processes are especially likely to be influenced by hydrodynamic compaction. Among these are some of the most important and promising processes for industrial usage of composites (e.g. VARI, Advanced RTM). Therefore, this topic is highly relevant and deeper insights have to be generated. One of the main questions in this paper concerned the adequate experimental possibilities for the evaluation of the hydrodynamic compaction behavior of textiles. The comparison of saturated and unsaturated compaction and permeability measurements pointed out, that saturation has a strong influence. The comparison with the new measurement cell, which allows compaction tests at simultaneous flow, showed that also tremendous differences result from the flow. Therefore, it can be concluded, that separate permeability and compaction tests are useful for the qualitative investigation of parameter influences on the compaction and permeability behavior, but insufficient for the generation of data required for accurate process control and simulation. The study revealed new phenomena, caused by simultaneous flow, which cannot be neglected. It delivers new data required to describe the true behavior during impregnation. However, the study with the new cell is not extensive enough for final conclusions to the many phenomena observed. The flow rate – dependent V_F -distribution and the transition from unsaturated to saturated state require further investigations.

5 Conclusions

Two main questions were investigated in this paper. The first one was how manufacturing process parameters and material parameters influence the

compaction behavior of textiles during the impregnation. The results point out, that concerning the process parameters few pre-compaction, high injection pressures (eventually caused by high tool closing velocity), few shearing, a high number of layers, homogeneous stacking, consecutive compaction cycles and a high degree of saturation increase the occurring of hydrodynamic compaction. Concerning the textiles it was shown that increasing stitching length, increasing yarn linear density, and the usage of 0/90° material instead of ±45° material tend to increase the resistance against deformation of non-crimp fabrics, while the stitching type has no influence. The resistance of woven fabrics against deformation is increased when the linear or yarn density is decreased or the number of crossing points is increased. Also the finish has a tremendous influence.

The second question concerned the proper method for data generation required to describe the behavior of a textile in a real manufacturing process. The results show that simultaneous flow strongly increases the resistance against deformation when V_F is low. At higher fiber volume contents the influence can switch. Also it was shown that the measured permeability values were pressure-related. Further research is required to investigate this issue. These results point out that separate measurements can be useful for the estimation of compaction behavior but are insufficient for the generation of data required for accurate simulation and process parameter and textile selection. New measurement devices - like the one presented here - are necessary.

Fig. 2. Set-up for the compaction measurements on the universal testing machine

Fig. 3. Illustration of a cross section of the new measurement device

Fig. 1. Derivation of pressure optimization problem

Fig. 4. Development of pressure drop and stack deformation (measured by LVDT 1-3) over experiment time (SCC 3106, 12 layers, initial cavity height: 4.96 mm)

Fig. 5. Comparison of unsaturated, saturated and hydrodynamic compaction tests (at 3 different initial fiber volume contents) for material GF-6; the dashed curves are the regression curves of the repetitive measurements

Fig. 6. Comparison of unsaturated, saturated and hydrodynamic compaction tests (at 3 different initial fiber volume contents) for material GF-9; the dashed curves are the regression curves of the repetitive measurements

Fig. 7. Comparison of unsaturated permeability tests for material GF-8 with saturated permeability tests including hydrodynamic compaction measurement (at three different initial fiber volume contents); the dashed curves are the regression curves of the repetitive measurements

Table 1. Textile- and process-related influences on resistance against compaction found in the study

Fabric type	Textile parameters		Process parameters	
	Parameter	Influence on resistance against compaction when increased*	Parameter	Influence on resistance against compaction when increased/applied*
non-crimp	Stitching type	➔	Alternating stacking sequence	⬆
	Stitching length	⬆		
	Stitching yarn linear density	⬆		
	fiber orientations	(0°/90° shows higher resistance than ±45°)	Number of consecutive compaction cycles	⬇
woven	Linear density of yarns	⬇	Shear angle	⬆
	Number of crossing points	⬆	Number of layers	⬆
	Yarn density	⬇	Grade of saturation	⬇
	Finish	⬇ / ⬆ / ➔	Compaction velocity	⬆

*most common finding of this study, if contrary findings were observed

Table 2. Material data and compaction test results of glass fiber woven fabrics

No.	Manufacturer and notation	Weave	Yarn-density (warp) [picks/cm]	Yarn-density (weft) [picks/cm]	Linear density (warp) [g/km]	Linear density (weft) [g/km]	Areal weight [g/m²]	Filament (warp-/weft)	Pressure at 50% fiber volume content [bar]*	Coefficient of variation [%]
GF-1	PGTex #1	twill 2/2	7.45	7.45	272	272	408.54	EC9-34x2	1.02 / -	5.64 / -
GF-2	PGTex #2	twill 2/2	7.45	7.45	136	136	202.83	EC9-34x2	6.87 / -	11.39 / -
GF-3	PGTex #3	twill 2/2	7.45	7.45	272	136	305.73	EC9-34x2	2.00 / -	10.88 / -
GF-4	PGTex #4	twill 2/2	7.45	7.45	136	272	303.45	EC9-34x2	2.10 / -	4.83 / -
GF-5	PGTex #5	twill 2/2	7.45	7	204	204	291.76	EC9-34x2	1.75 / -	2.71 / -
GF-6	P-D Interglas Tech. 92105 FK144	plain	12	11.5	68	68	161.02	EC9-68	1.48 / 0.64	10.26 / 7.67
GF-7	P-D Interglas Tech. 92110 FK144	twill 2/2	12	11.5	68	68	160.13	EC9-68	3.15 / 1.17	4.44 / 17.4
GF-8	P-D Interglas Tech. 92626	8-harness satin	22	21	68	68	286.4	EC6-68	1.25 / 0.87	5.80 / 7.53
GF-9	Schlösser & Cramer 3106	twill 2/2	6	6.7	340	272	386.4	EC9-68x5	0.71 / 0.21	4.51 / 5.32
GF-10	Hexcel 1102	twill 2/2	7	7	204	204	284.79	EC9-68x3	1.55 / -	3.90 / -
GF-11	P-D Interglas Tech. 92125	twill 2/2	7	6.5	204	204	280.48	EC9-68x3/EC9-204	2.56 / -	6.50 / -
GF-12	Hexcel 1103	plain	7	7	204	204	285.68	EC9-68x3	1.16 / -	13.73 / -
GF-13	Hexcel 1035	twill 2/2	14.7	14.7	68	68	202.81	EC9-68	3.05 / -	5.34 / -
GF-14	Hexcel 1039	twill 2/2	11.8	11.5	68	68	159.55	EC9-68	5.98 / -	0.88 / -
GF-15	P-D Interglas Tech. 92140FK200	twill 2/2	6	6.7	340	274	390	EC9-68x5 10	0.37 / -	6.19 / -
GF-16	P-D Interglas Tech. 92140FK600	twill 2/2	6	6.7	340	274	390	EC9-68x5 10	1.88 / -	4.15 / -
GF-17	P-D Interglas Tech. 92140FK801	twill 2/2	6	6.7	340	274	390	EC9-68x5 10	0.74 / -	2.34 / -

* Average of three measurements, all with 10 layers; unsaturated / saturated

Table 3: Material data and compaction test results of non-crimp carbon fiber fabrics

No.	Manufacturer and Notation	Built-up / carbon fiber yarn			Stitching yarn					Experimental		
		Orientation angle [°]	Area weight [g/m²]	Roving - Linear density [g/km]	Linear density [g/km]	Stitching density [1/inch]	Mass [g/m²]	Stitching type	Stitching length [mm]	Pressure at 50% fiber volume content [bar]*	Coefficient of variation [%]	Shearing angle
CF-1	Sigmatex DMC271 1270	+/-45	304	1600	360	E5	4	Hybrid	2.86	0.3	13	0°
CF-2	Sigmatex DMC301 1270	+/-45	304	1600	800	E5	6	Hybrid	2.86	0.46/0.72	12/5	0°/10°
CF-3	Sigmatex DMC302 1270	+/-45	304	1600	360	E5	4	Hybrid	5	0.76/0.93	8/13	0°/10°
CF-4	Sigmatex DMC303 1270	+/-45	304	1600	360	E2.5	4	Chain	2.86	0.25/0.25	3/6	0°/10°
CF-5	Sigmatex DMC304 1270	0/90	304	1600	800	E5	6	Hybrid	2.86	1.31/1.66	8/18	0°/10°
CF-6	Sigmatex DMC305 1270	0/90	304	1600	360	E5	4	Hybrid	5	0.91/1.36	4/4	0°/10°

* average of three measurements, all unsaturated and with 6 layers

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